

and figure). Yuanfengzao and Zhe 85-2 that headed at >35 °C had higher SFP (76.8, and 76.2, respectively) than Erjiunan 1 and Erjiufeng (34.9 and 58.1,

respectively).

There was a significantly negative correlation between SFP and mean daily maximum temperature (MMT) 3 d

after heading. SFP decreased with increasing MMT. The critical day for significantly decreased SFP was 30 Jun, when MMT was 35.9 °C for 3 d. □

Grain quality and nutritional value

Using silica gel desiccant to dry rough rice samples

P. A. Clarke, Overseas Development Natural Resources Institute (ODNRI), Culham, Abingdon, Oxon OX14 5PR, UK; and M. A. Quasem, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Gazipur, Bangladesh

The method and rate by which rough rice is dried changes the characteristics by which grain quality is judged. We have developed a method that achieves high standardization of large numbers of small samples of grain (less than 1 kg). It is based on the sorptive capacity of a special grade of silica gel mixed directly with field-wet rice.

Intermediate density (ID) grade silica gel is dried, cooled, mixed with field-wet rice in the ratio 1:2 by weight, and the mixture sealed in a moistureproof container. After 24 h, the 2 constituents are separated by screening.

The figure shows the linear regression of field (input) moisture content on residual (output) moisture content within 20–30% wet basis for the model

$$Y = 4.17 \times 0.38; r = 0.91, p = 0.01.$$

Effect of contact mix with ID silica gel on rice input and output moisture content.

Grain quality was measured as grain breakage on milling. The table compares gel-dried samples with sun- and air-dried samples. The gel technique produced

results at least as good as, and some better than, traditional methods, with higher control and resource optimization. □

Moisture content and milling quality of rice dried in a contact mix with ID silica gel and by air and sun.

Drying process	Moisture content (%)		Milling quality (% brown rice)	
	Initial	Residual	Degree of milling	Broken grain
				BR1
Gel	19.2	12.4	16.1 a	20.2 a
Air	19.2	14.3	15.8 a	21.2 ab
Sun	19.2	14.1	15.9 a	21.7 b
				BR3
Gel	24.6	13.7	13.5 a	10.4 a
Air	24.6	14.1	13.0 a	10.4 a
Sun	24.6	14.5	12.5 a	9.1 a
				BR4
Gel	27.1	14.5	13.2 a	5.0 a
Air	27.1	15.6	13.9 b	5.3 a
Sun	27.1	13.2	13.0 a	5.6 a
				BR10
Gel	28.9	15.2	14.0 a	6.2 ab
Air	28.9	14.8	15.1 b	6.6 b
Sun	28.9	13.9	14.4 a	5.9 a

In a column for a variety, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different by DMRT at $p = 0.05$.

Disease resistance

Resistance to sheath blight (ShB) in China

Xue-Yan Sha and Li-Hong Zhu, Nanjing Agricultural University, Nanjing, China

ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* [Thanatephorus cucumeris (Frank) Donk] is a major disease in the rice areas along the middle and lower reaches of the Yangtze River and in South China. In 1985–87, we used Tetep, IET4699, Jawa no. 14, and Yedao as resistance donors and IR9752-71-3-2 as

susceptible parent to study the inheritance of reaction to artificial ShB inoculation at booting by virulent isolate RH-9, collected in Jiangsu Province.

The F₁ of four combinations of moderately resistant and susceptible parents showed intermediate reaction to inoculation; the F₂ distributions tended to be continuous. That implies that resistance to ShB is controlled by multiple genes (see figure). Broad and narrow sense heritabilities estimated from the cross IR9752-71-3-2/IET4699 were $h^2B = 0.516 + 0.0654$ (broad) and $h^2N = 0.373 + 0.063$ (narrow).

Analysis of combining abilities based on the performance of 28 diallelic F₁s

Distribution of resistance to ShB in F₂ of PI-Tetep, P₂-IET4699, P₃-Jawa no. 14, P₄-Yedao, and P₈-IR9752-71-3-2.

Analysis of variance in combining abilities of reactions to rice ShB, 1986.

Source of variation	DF	Sum of squares	Mean square	F values ^a	
				Model 1	2
General combining ability	7	16.0891	2.2984	257.67**	18.87**
Specific combining ability	20	10.5383	0.5269	59.07**	4.33**
Error Model 1	924		0.0089		
2	54		0.1218		

^a** = significant at 0.01.

without reciprocals among Tetep, IET4699, Mianhuatiao, Jawa no. 14, Yedao, 84-3019, Shuidaobawang, and IR9752-71-3-2 showed that general combining abilities were more prominent than specific combining abilities. That means that additive gene effects play a more important role in inheritance of resistance to ShB (see table). It would not be possible to derive

an elite line with a resistance level similar or superior to that of moderately resistant parents through recurrent selection. □

For information on ordering IRRI publications, write Communication and Publications Dept., Div. R, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

A new inoculation technique for rice blast (BI)

Sun Guochang and Sun Shuyuan, Plant Protection Institute, Zhejiang Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Hangzhou; and Shen Zongtan, Agronomy Department, Zhejiang Agricultural University, Hangzhou, China

We studied a smear method for inoculating with the rice BI pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. for resistance screening. Smear inoculation conditions are similar to natural infection.

The method requires only a small amount of spore suspension and gives a high infection frequency. Inoculation is carried out by smearing the mixture $1-2 \times 10^5$ conidia/ml suspended in 1-2% carboxymethyl cellulose onto the rice leaf with a brush.

The method is suitable for inoculation at several stages, but especially at the 2-4-leaf stage. A spore suspension of 1×10^5 conidia/ml gives nearly 100% leaf infection. Smear inoculation produces a higher disease index than spray inoculation, but lower than injection inoculation (Table 1).

This method also is useful as a simple and precise method for evaluating neck BI resistance (Table 2). □

Table 1. Effect of smear inoculation on leaf BI. Hangzhou, China, 1987.

Variety	BI index ^a			BI score ^b		
	Injection	Smear	Spraying	Injection	Smear	Spraying
<i>Indica</i>						
Chei-Tang	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nong 8506	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gui-Chao 2	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hou-Zeng-Zao	5.6	4.9	1.5	0.5	0.4	0.1
Zao-Shuang 1	14.8	14.3	4.0	1.3	1.3	0.4
Zhong 83-40	69.6	29.4	17.8	6.3	2.6	1.6
Zhong 83-49	76.4	68.6	45.5	6.9	6.2	4.1
Hong-Tu 3	86.9	71.2	48.9	7.8	6.4	4.4
B40	83.0	80.4	45.8	7.5	7.2	4.1
8004	96.9	73.9	48.3	8.7	6.6	4.4
Er-Jiu-Qing	95.1	85.8	53.5	8.6	7.7	4.8
Zuo 5	94.8	80.4	56.2	8.5	7.2	5.1
<i>Japonica</i>						
Pi-4	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kusabue	18.3	24.3	3.5	1.6	2.2	0.3
BL 1	87.2	52.4	41.0	7.8	4.7	3.7
Dong-Nong 363	71.8	68.6	42.7	6.5	6.2	3.8
Li-Jiang-Xing-Tuan-He-Guo	100.0	100.0	92.4	9.0	9.0	8.3

^aDisease index = $\frac{\sum(\text{number of plants with a given score} \times \text{value of that score})}{\text{total number of plants} \times \text{value of the highest score}}$

^bBased on Standard evaluation system for rice.

Table 2. Effect of smear inoculation on neck BI. Hangzhou, China, 1987.

Inoculation method	Plants (no.)	Plants with BI infection (no.)	Infection frequency (%)
Injection	10	10	100.00
Gear	22	22	100.00
Spraying	10	6	60.0

Rice sheath blotch incidence in Haryana

U. Bhan and S. C. Ahuja, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi, India

Sheath blotch caused by *Pyrenochaeta oryzae* Shirai ex Miyake is increasing in